

Mediating Role of Entrepreneurial Mindset on the Effect of Entrepreneurial Education and Self-Efficacy on Entrepreneurial Intention Among University Undergraduates

Nuruddeen Abubakar and Muhammad Adamu

Received: 23 January 2026/Accepted: 24 May 2026 /Published: 04 June 2026

<https://dx.doi.org/10.4314/cps.v13i6.9>

Abstract : *This study investigates the Mediating role of entrepreneurial mindset on the effect of entrepreneurial education and self-efficacy on entrepreneurial intention among university undergraduates. Utilizing the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), the research examines how entrepreneurship education and self-efficacy impact entrepreneurial intention, with entrepreneurial mindset as a mediator. A cross-sectional survey design was employed, targeting 45,957 undergraduates across three universities in Bauchi State, with a sample of 418 students selected via stratified sampling. Data were collected using a validated Likert-scale questionnaire and analyzed through Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) to assess direct and mediating effects. The pilot study confirmed the reliability (Cronbach's Alpha > 0.7) and validity (AVE > 0.5) of the instrument. The findings of this study revealed that entrepreneurial education and self-efficacy all have a significant positive effect on the entrepreneurial intention of university undergraduates, the study established that entrepreneurial mindset significantly mediates these relationships. Based on the findings the study recommends educational institutions should offer targeted training that combines self-efficacy-building activities, such as leadership development and decision-making simulations, with mindset-focused interventions like goal-setting workshops.*

Keywords: *Entrepreneurial Intention; Entrepreneurial Education; Self Efficacy; Entrepreneurial Mindset*

Nuruddeen Abubakar

Department of Business Administration,
Faculty of Management Sciences, Sa'adu
Zungur University, Gadau, Bauchi, Bauchi
State, Nigeria.

Email: nuruddeenkobi@gmail.com

<https://orcid.org/0009-0001-5671-071X>

Muhammad Adamu

Department of Business Administration,
Faculty of Management Sciences, Sa'adu
Zungur University, Gadau, Bauchi, Bauchi
State, Nigeria.

Email: madamu@sazu.edu.ng

1.0 Introduction

Entrepreneurship has become a critical driver of economic growth, innovation, employment generation, and social transformation across the world. In both developed and developing economies, entrepreneurial activities contribute significantly to reducing unemployment, creating wealth, and enhancing national competitiveness (Cuong, 2025). As global economies continue to experience rapid technological, demographic, and structural changes, governments and educational institutions increasingly recognize entrepreneurship as a viable pathway for addressing youth unemployment and promoting sustainable economic development (Isa et al., 2024). Consequently, fostering entrepreneurial intention among university students has emerged as a major policy and academic concern.

Entrepreneurial intention refers to an individual's conscious state of mind and commitment toward starting a new business venture in the future. It is widely recognized

as the most immediate antecedent of entrepreneurial behavior and venture creation (Maradiaga-López et al., 2026). Among university undergraduates, entrepreneurial intention is particularly important because it reflects students' willingness to translate acquired knowledge, skills, and competencies into entrepreneurial action upon graduation. The Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) posits that entrepreneurial intention is influenced by cognitive and psychological factors such as attitudes, perceived behavioral control, subjective norms, and self-beliefs, all of which shape an individual's readiness to engage in entrepreneurial activities (Isa et al., 2024; Sunoma & Adamu, 2026).

Entrepreneurship education has been identified as one of the most important institutional mechanisms for promoting entrepreneurial intention among students. Entrepreneurship education equips learners with entrepreneurial knowledge, business management skills, opportunity recognition abilities, and practical competencies required for venture creation. Empirical studies have consistently reported positive relationships between entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial outcomes. For instance, Wu et al. (2022) found that entrepreneurship education significantly enhances entrepreneurial self-efficacy and entrepreneurial intention among Chinese university students. Similarly, Cuong (2025) reported that entrepreneurship education positively influences entrepreneurial mindset, entrepreneurial self-efficacy, and entrepreneurial intention among Vietnamese students. Entrepreneurship education not only imparts knowledge but also develops entrepreneurial thinking patterns that enable students to identify opportunities, evaluate risks, and pursue innovative solutions to societal problems.

Another important determinant of entrepreneurial intention is entrepreneurial self-efficacy. Entrepreneurial self-efficacy

refers to an individual's belief in his or her capability to successfully perform entrepreneurial tasks and establish a business venture. According to Social Cognitive Theory, individuals who possess high self-efficacy are more likely to exhibit confidence, persistence, resilience, and willingness to undertake challenging entrepreneurial activities. Several empirical studies have demonstrated the significant role of self-efficacy in predicting entrepreneurial outcomes. Wu et al. (2022) established that entrepreneurial self-efficacy completely mediates the relationship between entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial intention. Likewise, Adeniyi (2023) found that entrepreneurial self-efficacy significantly mediates the relationship between entrepreneurship education and start-up readiness among Nigerian students. More recently, Sunoma and Adamu (2026) reported that entrepreneurial self-efficacy strengthens the effects of digital competence and entrepreneurship education on digital entrepreneurial intention among university students in North-Eastern Nigeria.

Beyond education and self-efficacy, increasing attention has been directed toward the concept of entrepreneurial mindset. Entrepreneurial mindset refers to a set of attitudes, cognitive orientations, beliefs, and behavioral tendencies that enable individuals to identify opportunities, tolerate uncertainty, innovate, and create value through entrepreneurial activities. An entrepreneurial mindset influences how individuals perceive opportunities and challenges and determines whether acquired entrepreneurial knowledge is transformed into entrepreneurial action. Isa et al. (2024) argue that entrepreneurship education plays a significant role in shaping entrepreneurial mindset among university students, thereby enhancing their entrepreneurial potential. Similarly, Ganbat et al. (2023) found that entrepreneurship education significantly influences

entrepreneurial mindset, which subsequently enhances entrepreneurial intention among undergraduate students. These findings suggest that entrepreneurial mindset serves as an important psychological mechanism linking educational experiences to entrepreneurial outcomes.

Recent studies have increasingly highlighted the mediating role of psychological factors in explaining how entrepreneurship education influences entrepreneurial intention. Maradiaga-López et al. (2026) demonstrated that entrepreneurship education affects entrepreneurial intention primarily through indirect pathways involving entrepreneurial self-efficacy and entrepreneurial motivation. Likewise, Cuong (2025) found that entrepreneurial mindset mediates the relationship between entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial intention among university students. These findings support the argument that entrepreneurship education alone may not be sufficient to stimulate entrepreneurial intention unless it fosters the psychological dispositions and cognitive frameworks necessary for entrepreneurial action. Therefore, understanding the mediating mechanisms through which entrepreneurship education and self-efficacy influence entrepreneurial intention remains an important area of scholarly inquiry.

Despite the growing body of literature, several gaps remain. First, although numerous studies have examined the direct effects of entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial self-efficacy on entrepreneurial intention, limited attention has been given to the mediating role of entrepreneurial mindset, particularly in developing-country contexts. Second, existing studies have largely focused on Asian and Latin American countries such as China, Malaysia, Vietnam, Mongolia, and Honduras (Isa et al., 2024; Cuong, 2025; Ganbat et al., 2023; Maradiaga-López et al., 2026), thereby limiting the generalizability of their findings

to Sub-Saharan Africa. Third, within Nigeria, available studies have predominantly examined the mediating role of entrepreneurial self-efficacy (Adeniyi, 2023; Sunoma & Adamu, 2026), while empirical evidence regarding the mediating role of entrepreneurial mindset remains scarce, especially among university undergraduates in North-Eastern Nigeria. Consequently, the psychological processes through which entrepreneurship education and self-efficacy translate into entrepreneurial intention among Nigerian students remain insufficiently understood.

Against this background, this study investigates the mediating role of entrepreneurial mindset in the relationship between entrepreneurship education, entrepreneurial self-efficacy, and entrepreneurial intention among university undergraduates in Bauchi State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study seeks to determine the direct effects of entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial self-efficacy on entrepreneurial intention and to examine whether entrepreneurial mindset mediates these relationships.

The significance of this study is threefold. First, it contributes to the entrepreneurship literature by extending the Theory of Planned Behavior through the inclusion of entrepreneurial mindset as an important psychological mechanism linking entrepreneurship education and self-efficacy to entrepreneurial intention. Second, it provides empirical evidence from a developing-country context, particularly North-Eastern Nigeria, where research on entrepreneurial mindset remains limited. Third, the findings will offer valuable insights for policymakers, university administrators, curriculum developers, and entrepreneurship educators seeking to design interventions that not only provide entrepreneurial knowledge and skills but also cultivate the mindset necessary for entrepreneurial success.

Ultimately, the study contributes to efforts aimed at promoting entrepreneurship, reducing graduate unemployment, and fostering sustainable economic development in Nigeria.

2.0 Empirical Reviews and Hypotheses Formulation

2.1 Entrepreneurial Intention

Entrepreneurial intention represents an individual's cognitive commitment to engaging in entrepreneurial activities, such as launching a new venture or pursuing innovative projects. It is a psychological construct grounded in the interplay of personal motivations, attitudes, and external influences, often serving as a critical precursor to entrepreneurial behavior (Nwosu et al., 2022).

2.2 Entrepreneurship Education on Entrepreneurial Intention

Entrepreneurship education has been widely recognized as a critical determinant of entrepreneurial intention among university students. It equips students with entrepreneurial knowledge, opportunity recognition skills, business management competencies, and the confidence required to pursue entrepreneurial careers. Empirical evidence indicates that entrepreneurship education positively influences students' entrepreneurial intentions by enhancing their entrepreneurial capabilities and preparedness. Wu et al. (2022) found that entrepreneurship education significantly improves entrepreneurial self-efficacy and entrepreneurial intention among Chinese university students. Similarly, Cuong (2025) reported that entrepreneurship education exerts a positive effect on entrepreneurial mindset, entrepreneurial self-efficacy, and entrepreneurial intention among students in Vietnam. Maradiaga-López et al. (2026) further established that entrepreneurship education influences entrepreneurial intention through capability beliefs and motivational factors. These findings suggest that

entrepreneurship education plays a significant role in stimulating entrepreneurial intention among university undergraduates. Therefore, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H01: Entrepreneurship education has no significant influence on the entrepreneurial intention of university undergraduates.

H01: Entrepreneurship Education has no Significant Influence on the Entrepreneurial Intention of University Undergraduates.

2.3 Self-Efficacy and Entrepreneurial Intention

Entrepreneurial self-efficacy refers to an individual's belief in his or her capability to successfully perform entrepreneurial tasks and establish a business venture. According to Social Cognitive Theory, individuals with high levels of self-efficacy are more likely to undertake challenging activities and persist in the face of obstacles. Empirical studies have consistently reported a positive relationship between entrepreneurial self-efficacy and entrepreneurial intention. Wu et al. (2022) found that entrepreneurial self-efficacy significantly predicts entrepreneurial intention and mediates the effect of entrepreneurship education on entrepreneurial intention. Similarly, Adeniyi (2023) reported that entrepreneurial self-efficacy positively influences start-up readiness among Nigerian students. Sunoma and Adamu (2026) further found that entrepreneurial self-efficacy significantly strengthens the relationship between entrepreneurship education and digital entrepreneurial intention among university students in North-Eastern Nigeria. These findings suggest that students who possess higher entrepreneurial self-efficacy are more likely to develop entrepreneurial intentions. Therefore, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H02: Self-efficacy has no significant effect on the entrepreneurial intention of university undergraduates.

2.4 The Mediating Role of Entrepreneurial Mindset in the Relationship between Entrepreneurship Education and Entrepreneurial Intention

Recent studies suggest that entrepreneurship education may influence entrepreneurial intention indirectly through psychological and cognitive mechanisms. Entrepreneurial mindset, characterized by opportunity recognition, innovativeness, resilience, and proactive thinking, has emerged as an important explanatory mechanism in entrepreneurship research. Isa et al. (2024) found that entrepreneurship education significantly contributes to the development of entrepreneurial mindset among university students. Likewise, Cuong (2025) reported that entrepreneurial mindset significantly mediates the relationship between entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial intention among students in Vietnam. Ganbat et al. (2023) further established that entrepreneurship education positively influences entrepreneurial mindset, which subsequently enhances entrepreneurial intention among undergraduate students. These findings indicate that entrepreneurial mindset may serve as an important mechanism through which entrepreneurship education translates into entrepreneurial intention. Therefore, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H03: Entrepreneurial mindset does not significantly mediate the relationship between entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial intention among university undergraduates.

2.5 The Mediating Role of Entrepreneurial Mindset in the Relationship between Self-Efficacy and Entrepreneurial Intention

Entrepreneurial self-efficacy has been identified as a key cognitive factor influencing entrepreneurial behaviour and intentions. Individuals with high self-efficacy tend to exhibit greater confidence, persistence, and

willingness to identify and exploit entrepreneurial opportunities. Such characteristics are closely associated with the development of an entrepreneurial mindset. Cuong (2025) found that entrepreneurial self-efficacy positively influences entrepreneurial mindset, which subsequently enhances entrepreneurial intention. Similarly, Ganbat et al. (2023) reported that entrepreneurial self-efficacy partially mediates the relationship between entrepreneurial mindset and entrepreneurial intention. These findings suggest that entrepreneurial mindset may provide an important psychological pathway through which self-efficacy influences entrepreneurial intention. Therefore, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H04: Entrepreneurial mindset does not significantly mediate the relationship between self-efficacy and entrepreneurial intention among university undergraduates.

2.6 Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) developed by Ajzen (1991). The theory posits that intention is the most immediate determinant of behaviour and is influenced by attitude toward the behaviour, subjective norms, and perceived behavioural control. In the context of entrepreneurship, perceived behavioural control is closely related to entrepreneurial self-efficacy, while entrepreneurship education contributes to the formation of positive entrepreneurial attitudes and beliefs. The theory provides a suitable framework for explaining how entrepreneurship education and self-efficacy influence entrepreneurial intention among university undergraduates. Furthermore, entrepreneurial mindset serves as an important cognitive mechanism through which entrepreneurial knowledge, beliefs, and competencies are translated into entrepreneurial intentions. Therefore, TPB provides a robust theoretical foundation for examining the direct and indirect relationships

among entrepreneurship education, self-efficacy, entrepreneurial mindset, and entrepreneurial intention.

2.7 Research Design

The study adopts a cross-sectional correlational survey research design to investigate the relationships among entrepreneurship education, self-efficacy, entrepreneurial mindset, and entrepreneurial intention among university undergraduates. The design is appropriate because it enables the examination of associations among variables without manipulating them and facilitates the generalization of findings to a larger population (Temizhan et al., 2022).

2.8 Reliability and Validity of Research Instruments

Reliability refers to the consistency and stability of measurement instruments over time (Sürücü & Maslakçı, 2020). The hypothesized relationships between these

constructs are illustrated in the research framework (Fig. 1). To ensure empirical accuracy, the reliability of these study constructs will be assessed using Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability (CR), with acceptable threshold values of 0.70 and above. Convergent validity will be evaluated using Average Variance Extracted (AVE), with a minimum acceptable value of 0.50, while discriminant validity will be assessed using the Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT). Specifically, entrepreneurship education and self-efficacy serve as independent variables, entrepreneurial mindset acts as the mediator, and entrepreneurial intention is the primary dependent outcome. These procedures will ensure that the measurement instruments adequately capture the constructs of entrepreneurship education, self-efficacy, entrepreneurial mindset, and entrepreneurial intention.

Fig. 1: Research Framework

2.9 Sample size

Using the Krejcie and Morgan (1970) table (Table 1), a population of 45,957 at a 95% confidence level with a 5% margin of error yields a sample size of 380. To account for potential non-responses, as suggested by McNamara et al. (2022), the sample size is increased by approximately 10%, resulting in a final sample of 418 undergraduates. The sample size for each university is determined

using Bowley's (1964) proportionate allocation formula, given as equation 1

$$n_h = \frac{N_h \times n}{N} \tag{1}$$

where n_h is the sample size for each institution, N_h is the population size for each institution, N is the population of the study and n is the total sample size.

Table 1: Krejcie and Morgan Sample Size Table

Population Size	Sample Size
10,000	370
20,000	377
50,000	381
100,000	384

3.10 Data Analysis

The data collected for the study was analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences software version 25 and smartPLS4. A sample size of 418 was used from the overall population of 45,957 of the study

Table 2: Instrument for Study Variables

Variables	Definition	Instrument	Source/Reference
Independent Variables			
Entrepreneurship Education	Entrepreneurship education refers to structured programs designed to equip students with knowledge, skills, and mindsets for identifying opportunities, launching ventures, and managing entrepreneurial activities.	Mean of responses for seven (7) item Likert-scale questionnaire assessing exposure to entrepreneurial courses, practical training, and mentorship.	Liñán & Chen (2009); Kusumojanto et al. (2021)
Self-Efficacy	Self-efficacy is an individual’s belief in their ability to successfully perform entrepreneurial tasks, such as opportunity recognition, resource mobilization, and risk management.	Mean of responses for seven (7) item Likert-scale questionnaire measuring confidence in entrepreneurial skills and capabilities.	Bandura (1977); Al-Qadasi et al. (2023)
Mediating Variable			
Entrepreneurial Mindset	The entrepreneurial mindset refers to the cognitive and attitudinal orientation that enables individuals to identify opportunities, embrace risk, and persist in pursuing entrepreneurial ventures..	Mean of responses for seven (7) item Likert-scale questionnaire assessing mindset for entrepreneurial activities.	Deci& Ryan (2000); Hassan et al. (2021)
Dependent Variable			
Entrepreneurial Intention	Entrepreneurial intention is an individual’s cognitive commitment to pursue entrepreneurial activities, such as starting a new	Mean of responses for seven (7) item Likert-scale questionnaire measuring intent to start a business within	Ajzen (1991); Cassol et al. (2022)

venture, within a specified timeframe. three years.

3.0 Results and Discussion

3.1 Results

The measurement model was used to test the reliability and validity of the measurement items by testing the factor loadings, composite reliabilities, and average variances extracted (AVE) of the measurement items. The measurement model was evaluated using indicator reliability, internal consistency reliability, convergent validity, and discriminant validity. Indicator reliability was assessed using outer loadings, with values above 0.70 considered ideal, although loadings above 0.50 were retained where composite reliability and AVE remained acceptable (Hair et al., 2019). Internal consistency reliability was assessed using Cronbach's Alpha (CA) and Composite Reliability (CR), while convergent validity was assessed using Average Variance Extracted (AVE). (Subhaktiyasa 2024). Therefore, the factor loading less than 0.50 should be considered deleted. According to Shela et al., (2023) stated that Reflective indicator reliability Indicator loadings Loading >0.708 is recommended, but

loading >0.70, 0.6, 0.5 or 0.4 is adequate if other items have high scores of loadings to complement AVE and CR. the value of every specific Cronbach's Alpha(CA) coefficient in this study is within the range of 0.928 and 0.741, which is within the accepted value (Youssef et al., (2023). Also the value of every composite reliability (CR) factor fell in-between 0.940 and 0.727, as specified by Hair et al. (2019). To assess convergent validity, the value for every AVE fell in-between 0.693 to 0.551, which is within the suggested value of 0.50 and above (Koe et al., 2024).

As shown in Table 3, all constructs achieved acceptable levels of internal consistency reliability, with Cronbach's Alpha values ranging from 0.741 to 0.928 and Composite Reliability values ranging from 0.727 to 0.940. Furthermore, all AVE values exceeded the recommended threshold of 0.50, ranging from 0.551 to 0.693, thereby confirming convergent validity. Two indicators (EE4 and EE5) were removed because their factor loadings fell below the acceptable threshold.

Table 3: Convergent Validity of Measurement Model

Construct	Item	Loadings	CA	CR	AVE
Entrepreneurial Intention (EI)	EI1	0.797	0.818	0.857	0.664
	EI2	0.633			
	EI3	0.603			
	EI4	0.629			
	EI5	0.563			
	EI6	0.705			
	EI7	0.800			
Entrepreneurial Education (EE)	EE1	0.657	0.741	0.727	0.551
	EE2	0.516			
	EE3	0.518			
	EE6	0.548			
	EE7	0.699			
Self-efficacy (SE)	SE1	0.784	0.928	0.940	0.693
	SE2	0.894			
	SE3	0.826			
	SE4	0.732			
	SE5	0.907			

	SE6	0.732			
	SE7	0.926			
Entrepreneurship Mindset	EM1	0.816	0.823	0.870	0.593
	EM2	0.659			
	EM3	0.831			
	EM4	0.576			
	EM5	0.647			
	EM6	0.582			
	EM7	0.756			

Note:EE4 and EE5 were deleted

Table 4: Discriminant Validity (HTMT) Matrix

Constructs	EE	EI	EM	SE
Entrepreneurial Education (EE)				
Entrepreneurial Intention (EI)	0.616			
Entrepreneurial Mindset (EM)	0.338	0.499		
Self-Efficacy (SE)	0.544	0.359	0.292	

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Discriminant validity assessment is calculated using the Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT) criterion, which is considered a stronger method (Lame, et al., 2023). Ojoajogu et al., 2023 stated that all the values above 0.90 show discriminant validity issues. In the same vein, Chaudhry et al., (2023) submits that a value not above 0.85 shows there is no issue of discriminant validity in such data.

3.1.1 Finding (Hypotheses Testing)

The results for the direct effect hypotheses (H1, H2) are presented in Table 5. All the hypotheses show a significant positive effect on Entrepreneurial Intention. Entrepreneurial Education ($\beta = 0.464, p < 0.001$) was the strongest predictor. Self-Efficacy ($\beta = 0.025, p < 0.05$). Therefore H1 & H2 are supported.

Table 5: Significance Effects of Direct (Path Coefficient)

Constructs	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values	Decision
EE-> EI	0.464	0.174	0.069	11.114	0.000	Supported
SE -> EI	0.025	0.331	0.064	6.150	0.004	Supported

Source: Extracted from Smart PLS 4 outputs, 2025

The results for the moderating effects (H3, H4) are shown in Table 6. Entrepreneurial mindset significantly moderated the relationship between Entrepreneurial Education and

Entrepreneurial Intention ($\beta = 0.036, p = 0.013$) and between Self efficacy and Entrepreneurial Intention ($\beta = 0.082, p = 0.034$) all are supported.

Table 6: Moderating Effects

Constructs	Original Sample	T statistics	P	Decision
------------	-----------------	--------------	---	----------

	sample (O)	mean (M)	(O/STDEV)	values	
EE -> EM -> EI	0.036	0.154	2.644	0.013	Supported
SE -> EM -> EI	0.082	0.015	2.385	0.034	Supported

Source: Extracted from SmartPLS4 output, 2025.

3.2 Discussion

The findings of this study revealed that entrepreneurial education and self-efficacy have a significant positive effect on the entrepreneurial intention of university undergraduates. This implies that students who receive relevant entrepreneurship education, believe in their ability to perform entrepreneurial tasks, are more likely to develop strong entrepreneurial intentions. Furthermore, the study established that entrepreneurial mindset significantly mediates these relationships, indicating that mindset acts as a psychological bridge through which education and efficacy influence entrepreneurial intention.

3.2.1 Theoretical Support

The findings are consistent with the Theory of Planned Behavior (Ajzen, 1991), which posits that behavioural intention is influenced by attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioural control. In this study, entrepreneurial self-efficacy represents perceived behavioural control, while entrepreneurship education contributes to the development of positive attitudes and competencies that strengthen entrepreneurial intention. The mediating role of entrepreneurial mindset confirms the argument that mindset shapes the translation of knowledge and attitudes into behavioral intention, thereby strengthening the theoretical linkage between cognition and action

The significant mediating role of entrepreneurial mindset suggests that entrepreneurship education and self-efficacy alone may not be sufficient to stimulate entrepreneurial intention. Rather, these factors influence entrepreneurial intention

through the development of opportunity recognition, resilience, innovation orientation, and risk-taking propensity. This finding supports the argument of Cuong (2025) and Ganbat et al. (2023), who reported that entrepreneurial mindset serves as an important cognitive mechanism linking entrepreneurial competencies to entrepreneurial intention.

3.2.2 Empirical Support

The findings of this study are consistent with existing empirical evidence on entrepreneurial intention among university students. The significant positive effect of entrepreneurship education on entrepreneurial intention supports the findings of Utami et al. (2025), who reported that entrepreneurship education enhances students' entrepreneurial intention by improving entrepreneurial knowledge and competencies. Similarly, Wu et al. (2022) and Cuong (2025) found that entrepreneurship education positively influences entrepreneurial intention by strengthening entrepreneurial skills and confidence.

The significant effect of self-efficacy on entrepreneurial intention is consistent with the findings of Adeniyi (2023), who reported that entrepreneurial self-efficacy positively influences entrepreneurial readiness among students. Likewise, Sunoma and Adamu (2026) found that entrepreneurial self-efficacy strengthens the relationship between entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial intention among university students.

Furthermore, the significant mediating role of entrepreneurial mindset supports the findings of Cuong (2025), Ganbat et al. (2023), and

Isa et al. (2024), who reported that entrepreneurial mindset serves as a critical psychological mechanism through which entrepreneurship education and self-efficacy translate into entrepreneurial intention. These findings collectively suggest that entrepreneurial intention is not solely determined by educational exposure or confidence in entrepreneurial abilities but also depends on the extent to which students develop an entrepreneurial mindset characterized by innovation, opportunity recognition, resilience, and proactive behaviour.

4.0 . Conclusion

This study provides a comprehensive examination of the determinants of entrepreneurial intention among university undergraduates in Bauchi State, Nigeria, with a particular focus on the mediating role of the entrepreneurial mindset. By integrating entrepreneurship education, self-efficacy, and social attitudes within the framework of the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), the research elucidates how these factors interact to shape students' intentions to pursue entrepreneurial ventures. The findings underscore the critical role of entrepreneurship education in equipping students with practical skills and knowledge, which, when combined with a robust entrepreneurial mindset characterized by resilience, opportunity recognition, and autonomy, significantly enhances their intention to launch ventures. In the Nigerian context, where high youth unemployment and necessity-driven entrepreneurship prevail, these insights are vital for designing educational interventions that bridge the gap between intention and action.

The mediating role of the entrepreneurial mindset emerges as a pivotal mechanism that channels the effects of education, self-efficacy, and societal attitudes into actionable entrepreneurial intentions. The study highlights that a well-developed mindset,

fostered through experiential learning and exposure to role models, can amplify the impact of educational programs and boost students' confidence in their entrepreneurial capabilities.

5.0 References

- Abba, D., Adamu, M., Aliyu, A. S., & Inuwa, S. (2022). Effect of environmental factors on entrepreneurship development in Bauchi State. *Yamtara Wala Journal of Arts, Management and Social Sciences*, 2, 2, pp. 327–339.
- Adeniyi, A. O. (2023). The mediating effects of entrepreneurial self-efficacy in the relationship between entrepreneurship education and start-up readiness. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 10, Article 801. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-023-02296-4>
- Adeyemi, A. E., & Ojo, S. A. (2023). Enhancing sustainable development in Nigeria through entrepreneurship education. In *Lead City University Postgraduate Multidisciplinary Conference Proceedings*, 1, 3, pp. 187–201.
- Al-Qadasi, N., Zhang, G., Al-Awlaqi, M. A., Alshebami, A. S., & Aamer, A. (2023). Factors influencing entrepreneurial intention of university students in Yemen: The mediating role of entrepreneurial self-efficacy. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 14, 1111934,
- Apostu, S. A., Mukli, L., Panait, M., Gigauri, I., & Hysa, E. (2022). Economic growth through the lenses of education, entrepreneurship, and innovation. *Administrative Sciences*, 12, 3, 74, <https://doi.org/10.3390/admsci12030074>
- Cassol, A., Tonial, G., Machado, H. P. V., Dalbosco, I. B., & Trindade, S. (2022). Determinants of entrepreneurial intentions and the moderation of entrepreneurial education: A study of the

- Brazilian context. *The International Journal of Management Education*, 20, 3, Article 100716, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijme.2022.100716>.
- Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN). (2024). Central Bank of Nigeria intervention fund and entrepreneurial growth in Nigeria. *African Journal of Business and Economic Research*, 19, 4, https://hdl.handle.net/10520/ejc-aa_ajber_v19_n4_a13
- Chaudhry, M. G., Hameed, Z., & Ahmed, F. (2023). Effect of abusive supervision on organizational cynicism (cognitive, affective, behavioral): Mediating effect of playing dumb. *PLoS ONE*, 18, 4, Article e0284884, doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0284884
- Coad, A., Domnick, C., Santoleri, P., & Srhoj, S. (2025). Does Africa need entrepreneurial ecosystems thinking? *The Journal of Technology Transfer*, pp. 1–27.
- Csákné Filep, J., Szennay, Á., & Tímár, G. (2024). *Opportunities, motivation, environment: GEM 2024 report*.
- Cuong, D. T. (2025). Influence of entrepreneurial education on students' entrepreneurial intent: Mediating roles of entrepreneurial self-efficacy and mindset. In *2024 Yearbook Emerging Technologies in Learning* (pp. 22–34). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-80388-8_22
- Dattalo, N. (2019). Relationship between organisational effectiveness and project performance of SME contractors: A developing country perspective. *Journal of Construction Business and Management*, 3, 2, pp. 1–16.
- Ganbat, D., Zanabazar, A., & Chen, S. H. (2023). The correlation between entrepreneurship education, entrepreneurial mindset, and entrepreneurial intention among undergraduate students: The mediating function of entrepreneurial self-efficacy. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship*, 27, 5, pp. 1–16.
- Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (GEM). (2024). *GEM 2023/2024 global report: 25 years and growing*.
- Hassan, A., Anwar, I., Saleem, I., Islam, K. B., & Hussain, S. A. (2021). Individual entrepreneurial orientation, entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial intention: The mediating role of entrepreneurial motivations. *Industry and Higher Education*, 35, 4, pp. 403–418.
- Hemsworth, D., Muterera, J., Khorakian, A., & Garcia-Rivera, B. R. (2024). Exploring the theory of employee planned behavior: Job satisfaction as a key to organizational performance. *Psychological Reports*, 129, 2, <https://doi.org/10.1177/00332941241252784>
- Isa, A. S., Razak, M. I. M., & Husain, N. A. (2024). The mediating role of entrepreneurial education on entrepreneurial mindset among public university students in Malaysia. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 14, pp. 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.6007/IJARBS/v14-i11/23178>
- Koe, W. L., et al. (2024). [Complete reference required].
- Koseoglu, M. A., & Arici, H. E. (2025). An empirical analysis of the entrepreneurial ecosystem and its impact on economic growth across different income levels. *Journal of Entrepreneurship and Public Policy*, <https://doi.org/10.1108/JEPP-09-2024-0158>
- Kusumojanto, D. D., Wibowo, A., Kustiandi, J., & Narmaditya, B. S. (2021). Do entrepreneurship education and environment promote students'

- entrepreneurial intention? The role of entrepreneurial attitude. *Cogent Education*, 8, 1, Article 1948660, <https://doi.org/10.1080/2331186X.2021.1948660>
- Lame, K. M., Inuwa, M., & Ojoajogu, A. M. (2023). Mediating role of work motivation on behavioral work environment and employee productivity of Bauchi State civil servants. *International Journal of Intellectual Discourse*, 6, 4, pp. 211–223.
- Lihua, D. (2022). An extended model of the theory of planned behavior: An empirical study of entrepreneurial intention and entrepreneurial behavior in college students. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12, Article 627818, <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.627818>
- Liñán, F., & Chen, Y. W. (2009). Development and cross-cultural application of a specific instrument to measure entrepreneurial intentions. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 33, 3, pp. 593–617.
- Lusha, E. (2023). Emerging economic patterns in developing countries. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Research and Development*, 10, 3, pp. 66–66.
- Maradiaga-López, J., Álvarez, O., & Osorto, H. (2026). Entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial intention among university students: The mediating roles of entrepreneurial self-efficacy and motivation. *Sustainability*, 18, Article 3985. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su18083985>
- McNamara, J., O'Shaughnessy, B. R., O'Hagan, A. D., Burke, A., & O'Connor, S. (2022). The prevalence of farmer burnout: Systematic review and narrative synthesis. *Journal of Rural Studies*, 96, pp. 282–292.
- Müller, F. H., Thomas, A. E., Carmignola, M., Dittrich, A. K., Eckes, A., Großmann, N., & Bieg, S. (2021). University students' basic psychological needs, motivation, and vitality before and during COVID-19: A self-determination theory approach. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12, Article 775804.
- Nwosu, H. E., Obidike, P. C., Ugwu, J. N., Udeze, C. C., & Okolie, U. C. (2022). Applying social cognitive theory to placement learning in business firms and students' entrepreneurial intentions. *The International Journal of Management Education*, 20, 1, Article 100602.
- Ojoajogu, A. M., Inuwa, M., & Lame, K. M. (2023). Moderating effect of organizational trust on customer relationship management and organizational performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria. *International Journal of Intellectual Discourse*, 6, 3, pp. 151–165.
- Rajar, A., Khoso, I. U., & Qureshi, M. B. (2022). Determinants of entrepreneurial intentions: Impact of culture, gender, self-esteem, and self-efficacy on university students. *Journal of Entrepreneurship, Management, and Innovation*, 4, 1, pp. 259–277.
- Schmitt, B., Brakus, J. J., & Biraglia, A. (2022). Consumption ideology. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 49, 1, pp. 74–95.
- Shela, V., Ramayah, T., Aravindan, K. L., Ahmad, N. H., & Alzahrani, A. I. (2023). Run! This road has no ending! A systematic review of PLS-SEM application in strategic management research among developing nations. *Heliyon*, 9, 12, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e22476>
- Silva, J. T. S., & de Almeida Leite, E. M. (2023). The role of education in developing an entrepreneurial mindset: Applications. *Perspectives and Trends in Education and Technology*, pp. 471–480.

- Su, Y., Zhu, Z., Chen, J., Jin, Y., Wang, T., Lin, C. L., & Xu, D. (2021). Factors influencing entrepreneurial intention of university students in China: Integrating perceived university support and the theory of planned behavior. *Sustainability*, 13, 8, Article 4519, DOI: [10.3390/su13084519](https://doi.org/10.3390/su13084519)
- Sunoma, K. Z. ., & Adamu, M. . (2026). Mediating role of entrepreneurial self-efficacy on the relationship between digital competence, entrepreneurship education and digital entrepreneurial intention of university students in north eastern Nigeria. *International Journal of Intellectual Discourse*, 9(1). Retrieved from <https://ijidjournal.org/index.php/ijid/article/view/1099>
- Temizhan, E., Mirtagioglu, H., & Mendes, M. (2022). Which correlation coefficient should be used for investigating relations between quantitative variables? *Academic Scientific Research Journal of Engineering, Technology and Sciences*, 85, 1, pp. 265–277.
- Utami, B., Ibrahim, M. M., Violin, V., Subroto, D. E., Destari, D., & Astuti, E. D. (2025). The role of entrepreneurship education, attitude toward risk and digital literacy on entrepreneurial intention among Gen Z. *Journal of Social Science and Business Studies*, 3, 1, pp. 407–411.
- Wang, X. H., You, X., Wang, H. P., Wang, B., Lai, W. Y., & Su, N. (2023). The effect of entrepreneurship education on entrepreneurial intention: Mediation of entrepreneurial self-efficacy and moderating model of psychological capital. *Sustainability*, 15, 3, pp. 1-20.
- Wu, L., Jiang, S., Wang, X., Yu, L., Wang, Y., & Pan, H. (2022). Entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial intentions of college students: The mediating role of entrepreneurial self-efficacy and the moderating role of entrepreneurial competition experience. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12, Article 727826. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.727826>
- Youssef, N., Saleeb, M., Gebreal, A., & Ghazy, R. M. (2023). The internal reliability and construct validity of the evidence-based practice questionnaire (EBPQ): Evidence from healthcare professionals in the Eastern Mediterranean Region. In *Healthcare*, 11, 15, Article 2168, doi: 10.3390/healthcare11152168.

Declarations:**Conflict of interest**

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest

Data availability

All data used in this study will be readily available to the public.

Consent for publication

Not Applicable.

Ethical consideration

Not applicable

Competing interests

The authors declared no conflict of interest.

Authors' Contributions

Nuruddeen Abubakar conceptualized the study, conducted the literature review, designed the methodology, collected and analyzed the data, and drafted the manuscript. Muhammad Adamu supervised the research, contributed to the study design, validated the analytical procedures, critically reviewed the manuscript for intellectual content, and approved the final version for publication. Both authors read and approved the final manuscript.

